

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.4.1: Natural hazards

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Description

Section 3.4.1 reviews the role of natural hazard as a drivers in facilitating the transport of species beyond their native ranges in Chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control.

Process overview

Protocol

- Type of analysis/search/review: literature review

- Search language(s): English

- **Search terms:** (("natural driver" OR "natural vector" OR "natural dispersal" OR "natural invasion") OR (hurricane OR storm OR "ocean current")) AND ((invasi* OR nonnative OR alien OR nonindigenous OR exotic) AND species)

- **Search engine:**
Web of Science

- **Date:** June 19, 2020

- **Searched time period:** 2000-2019

-**Selection Criteria:** Expert scrutiny in 2 steps: 1. applying additional search criteria (nonnative / nonindigenous/ alien/ invasive/ exotic) to remove papers that did not concern invasions (resulting in removal of 370 studies); then 2. Inspection of abstracts to insure the subject matter was appropriate.

- **Overview of the search results:**

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 11

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 27 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)